

CODAU

(Association of General Directors of Italian Universities)

Research Working Group

Sub-Working Group (WG)

**The role of the Research Manager and
Administrator - RMA, in Italy:
Professional framework and training needs**

2020 Activity Report

(April 2021)

Table of contents

Executive summary		
Context, objectives & perspectives	page	3
The RMA and the purpose of this role	page	5
Participants in the Working Group (WG)	page	5
Tasks and activities	page	6
Annexes		
I – WP1 Benchmarking table	page	10
II – WP2 Questionnaire structure	page	13
III – WP3 Questionnaire analysis	page	17
IV – WP4 A professional framework for the Research Manager & Administrator (RMA) role in Italy	page	22
V – WP6 Dissemination	page	30

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY- CODAU – *Research Working Group*

Sub-Working Group “The professional role of the Research Manager and Administrator, RMA, in Italy: professional framework and training needs”

The activities of the Sub-Working Group “**The professional role of the Research Manager and Administrator, RMA, in Italy: professional framework and training needs**” are carried out in the framework of the wider CODAU (Association of General Directors of Italian Universities) Research Group.

OBJECTIVES

The Sub-Working Group (hereinafter: “WG”) has been established with the **aim of analyzing and endorsing the professional role of the RMA in Italy, in particular through the creation of a model professional framework**, which identifies and maps the skills, areas of activity and training needs of Italian RMAs. The RMA profile has been herein defined at different professional levels, with the purpose of increasing awareness about the role and the potential of this function within the national RMA community.

CONTEXT

The creation of the WG is part of a debate on the complex ecosystem of research and innovation (R&I), where the **importance of human capital** is widely recognized as a fundamental asset. In fact, the effectiveness of activities such as promotion, management, development and communication of research and innovation in universities, depends on the ability of research institutions to encourage and to endorse initiatives aimed at improving the quality of scientific research. This is where the research support organizational units become an essential feature of and condition for research activities, as does the work of specialized staff, and particularly the Research Managers and Administrators (RMAs).

In this context, the role of the RMA is emerging as a global profession. Although an unambiguous definition of the professional role of the Research Manager and Administrator and its functions does not exist in literature, recent studies proved that in international university institutions the research support does not comply with the conventional definitions of "academic staff" and "non-academic staff".

RMAs are often considered as facilitators, i.e. interpreters and promoters of dialogue between the scientific community and the funding institutions, policy makers, businesses and citizens.

THE WG TASKS AND ACTIVITIES

The WG started its activities on 30th January 2020, with a kick off meeting held at the *Politecnico di Torino*, and followed up with more online meetings held via the Teams platform in plenary sessions (22 April 2020, 7 July 2020, 25 September 2020, 9 November, 22 December 2020, 22 January 2021).

With the purpose of creating a national professional framework for Italian RMAs, the WG agreed to use the definition of RMA provided by the project RAAAP, Research Administration as a Profession worldwide¹ as a

¹*Research Manager&Administrator: anyone whose activities and role or significant part of them are aimed at supporting the entire Research life cycle, including: strategic planning of research activities; planning of research support services; lobbying; networking activities; research promotion; planning support activities in the pre and post award phase (identification of funding sources and specific customers, support for the preparation of projects, dialogue and exchanges with areas/offices of the body / institution to which they belong - finance, personnel purchases in particular - reporting to the funding body); support and consultancy activities on the impact of research, innovation and research enhancement; support in planning training courses related to the activities carried out; research policy and strategy activities, research monitoring (assessment), research evaluation, data processing, research integrity, research communication, ethics and governance, IT systems, audits; activities to support the career development of researchers". Most research administrators work in universities or research institutes, but many work in research funders or other related organisations. <https://inorms.net/activities/raaap-taskforce/>*

reference and a starting point. Such appointment description fairly complies with the Italian RMA core activities, roles and objectives.

The WG has organized its tasks in subsequent work packages:

- WP1. **Benchmarking** - Analysis of 22 existing RMA associations at the international level in order to identify the **professional frameworks** and methods of identification of the RMA professional figure;
- WP2. Investigation of the Italian context - Drafting and dispatching of a **questionnaire to the Italian RMA community** aimed at identifying the professional levels, skills, activities, tasks and training needs of Italian RMAs;
- WP3. Data analysis - First **questionnaire analysis report**, based on the 259 answers to the questionnaire, aimed at outlining the main features of a professional framework for Italian RMAs;
- WP4. Outline of a **professional framework proposal** for Italian RMAs;
- WP5. Identification of training needs that RMAs are required to fulfill;
- WP6. Continuous dissemination of outcomes and further outreach – Building of an online **community of Italian RMAs** through the opening of a LinkedIn Group <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12369361/> (counting at present almost 100 subscribers); establishing contacts with Italian and European stakeholders as well as with European and international RMA associations, participation in dissemination events as to advertise the Italian initiative with the aim of establishing future collaborations and opportunities for exchange.

WHAT NEXT? FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The ultimate goal of the WG is the **promotion at the national level of the professional framework of the Italian RMA** – so that it may be formally recognized within the national professional system – and the definition of *ad hoc* training options and projects. The momentum is now, as the RMA profession is emerging both at the national and international level: a specific reference to the professional RMA profile can be found in programming documents adopted by the European Union, while the “*development of a new generation of research managers*” is stated as a priority in 2021-2027 (Italian) National Programme for Research (PNR – *Programma nazionale per la ricerca*). The upcoming negotiations for the update of the national contractual conditions of professionals working at Universities (*CCNL – Contratto Collettivo Nazionale dei Lavoratori*) make this time decisive for the actual development and adoption of the RMA professional framework and for the introduction of *ad hoc* trainings addressed to Italian RMAs. Such professional framework and training options will have to be consistent with the best practices in the field, which can be identified in the most advanced systems at the international level.

The WG has decided to form a permanent group, which will continue to enhance the professional figure of the RMA within the Italian community, strengthening its collaborations at the European and international level and performing activities related to the future professional recognition of the RMA profile (e.g. by designing *ad hoc* professional training).

WG MEMBERS

Coordinator: Politecnico di Torino (Valentina Romano) and University of Camerino (Annalisa Albanesi).

Participants: University of Ferrara (Adele Del Bello), University of Firenze (Laura Moretti), University of Milano Statale (Bruno Zampaglione, Mariella D’Alessio), University of Padua (Francesca Mura), University of Pisa (Michele Padrone), La Sapienza University of Rome, (Fausta Zurlo), University of “Roma Tor Vergata” (Danilo Aceto Zumbo), University of Siena (Donata Franzì, Claudia Rustici), University of Torino (Chiara Abrescia, Carmen Fiore), Politecnico di Torino (Silvia Infusino), University of Verona (Daniela Grisi).

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Sub-Working Group “The professional role of the Research Manager and Administrator, RMA, in Italy: professional framework and training needs”

THE RMA AND THE PURPOSE OF THIS ROLE

Who is the *Research Manager and Administrator (RMA)* and what is the purpose of this role?

For the purpose of creating a national professional framework, the WG agreed to use as a reference and starting point the definition of RMA that was developed by the project RAAAP, Research Administration as a Profession worldwide (<https://inorms.net/activities/raap-taskforce/>), which matches more closely the Italian RMA and may be adjusted to the Italian context:

The Research Manager&Administrator is a person working to support the research lifecycle process. This includes (but is not limited to) the following tasks: strategic planning of research activities, organisation of services supporting researchers, lobbying, networking, promotion of research, pre-award and post-award project support (i.e. scouting of funding opportunities, support to project management – from drafting to submission – and to budgeting and cost planning, handling of internal institutional relations, negotiations with funders, partnership management, supervision of financial report towards funders). Support and advising on research impacts, innovation and promotion, on training matters, on research policy, strategy and assessment and a number of topics such as data processing, research integrity, communication, ethics, governance, IT, audits, statutory returns, and career development of researchers.

Most RMAs work in universities or research institutes, but many researchers work in hospitals, institutions, charities, government bodies, corporations or other related organisations.

PARTICIPANTS IN THE WG

Coordinators: Politecnico di Torino (Valentina Romano) and University of Camerino (Annalisa Albanesi).

Participant Universities and staff: University of Ferrara (Adele Del Bello), University of Firenze (Laura Moretti), University of Milano Statale (Bruno Zampaglione, Mariella D’Alessio), University of Padova (Francesca Mura), University of Pisa (Michele Padrone), La Sapienza University of Rome, (Fausta Zurlo), University of “Roma Tor Vergata” (Danilo Aceto Zumbo), University of Siena (Donata Franzì), University of Torino (Chiara Abrescia, Carmen Fiore), Politecnico di Torino (Silvia Infusino), University of Verona (Daniela Grisi).

ACTIVITIES OF THE WORKING GROUP

The WG organized its activities as a project, creating different Work Packages (WPs). Each WP has a Leader and a Deputy, with the aim of engaging all the participant universities, while granting every party some specific independence.

The WG started its activities on 30th January 2020, with a kick off meeting held at the *Politecnico di Torino*, and followed up with more online meetings held via the Teams platform in plenary sessions (22nd April 2020, 7th July 2020, and 25th September 2020) plus some additional meetings among the participants to the respective WPs.

These meetings were intended as occasions to strengthen the relationships among WG members, to enhance the communication and to share the mutual objectives of the WG. They allowed to keep the WG network alive and running even during the challenging circumstances of the COVID-19 crisis.

Here below is a recap of the activities, partly carried out and partly to be completed (WIP – Work In Progress). The table specifies if specific resources (i.e. Annexes) have been drafted as a result of the activities performed in each WP.

WP	TASK	OUTPUT	WP LEADER & DEPUTY	OTHER PARTICIPANTS	STATUS & RESOURCES
WP1	Analysis of professional RMA frameworks worldwide	Benchmarking chart featuring specific professional framework and levels	Del Bello (UNIFE), Albanesi (UNICAM)	Romano (POLITO), Moretti (UNIFI), Rustici (UNISI)	Completed Annex I
WP2	Classification of professional levels and competencies, tasks and training needs for RMAs in Italy	Drafting and submission of professional profile questionnaire	Zurlo (SAPIENZA), Infusino (POLITO)	Aceto Zumbo (TOR VERGATA), Franzi (UNISI), Mura (UNIPD)	Completed Annex II
WP3	Definition of professional levels and competencies, tasks and training needs for RMAs in Italy	Analysis of questionnaire's responses	Aceto Zumbo (TOR VERGATA), Moretti (UNIFI)	Grisi (UNIVR), Zurlo (SAPIENZA), Infusino (POLITO), Franzi (UNISI), Mura (UNIPD)	Completed Annex III
WP4	Cross-analysis between levels and competencies	Drafting of Italian RMAs professional framework	Padrone (UNIPI), Zampaglione (UNIMI)	Del Bello (UNIFE), Albanesi (UNICAM), Fiore (UNITO), D'Alessio (UNIMI), Rustici (UNISI)	Completed Annex IV
WP5	Assessment and definition of training needs for Italian RMAs and analysis of existing programs	Plan of training programs for Italian RMAs	Romano (POLITO), Aceto Zumbo (TOR VERGATA)	Abrescia (UNITO), Fiore (UNITO), Franzi (UNISI), Mura (UNIPD)	WIP

WP6	Dissemination	Creation of Social Network profiles, participation to national and international conferences etc.	Abrescia (UNITO), Romano (POLITO)	ALL Participants	WIP
WP7	Management	Coordination of the WP activities, organization of formal and informal meetings, interaction between WPs	Romano (POLITO), Albanesi (UNICAM)	ALL Participants	WIP

Benchmarking activities (WP1), the questionnaire set up (WP2), the analysis of the questionnaire results (WP3), the development of a professional framework matrix proposal for Italian RMAs (WP4) have been finalized, while the analysis of *ad hoc* training and accreditation programs towards the proposal of training paths to be proposed in the Italian context, are being examined (WP5). The dissemination activities (WP6) started at the beginning of the work of the WG, as well as those relating to Management (WP7) and, since the WG, which is turning into a permanent team for 2021, are still in progress.

As for the identification of professional frameworks and training/accreditation models existing at the international level (WP1), the WG worked by comparing case studies, either through interviews to and/or website analysis of 22 RMA associations² (national, European and international). Activities within the European BESTPRAC project (COST Project), which aims at creating a network for the exchange of good practices between European RMAs, were also considered.

Information collected concerned the following features: size, age and purpose of associations, existence of professional frameworks (and related competences and skills), professional levels, training and accreditation/ acknowledgement of the professional role of RMA (for example through certifications). The output of this analysis was a benchmarking chart (Annex I). From the analysis between the associations, common traits emerged in some areas, despite the high level of heterogeneity. In particular, three commonly used professional levels emerged (Leader, Manager and Administrator) associated with diversified professional profiles, skills, areas of activity and training needs. There are **4 associations that have created a professional framework at national level (ARMA, ARMS, NARMA, SARIMA)**, while a European professional framework has been created as part of the EU BESTPRAC (Cost Action) project. Other associations are working on defining a framework; all of them organize *ad hoc* training courses intended for RMAs, according to their different levels and, in some cases, training courses accredited and certified by nationally recognized bodies.

The output of WP1 has represented the starting point for the work of WP2, which was dedicated to the conceptual and operational definition of RMA and that of professional levels and the identification of the basic elements of an Italian professional framework, to be collected through a questionnaire addressed to Italian RMAs. A questionnaire was drafted in order to identify the characteristics and training needs of RMAs in Italy.

Deliberately anonymous and easy to fill out, the questionnaire (Annex II) aimed at verifying who the Italian RMAs are in terms of **experiences, professional levels, work activities, training paths, skills (hard and soft skills), and training needs**. For this reason, it has been structured in three parts:

² Specifically, the following were considered: ARMA (UK), ARMA-NL (Netherlands) ARMS (Australia, New Zealand and Singapore), CARA-ACAAR (Canada), DARMA (Denmark), EARMA (Europe), Finn-ARMA (Finland), FORTRAMA (Germany), NARMA (Norway), NCURA (USA), RMAN-J (Japan), SARIMA (Southern Africa), Society of Research Administrators International – SRAI (USA).

- Part A - description of one's own experience as RMA;
- Part B - identification of training experiences;
- Part C - identification of training needs.

The definition of Research Manager and Administrator (RMA) was also included in the questionnaire, quoting the above mentioned RAAAP Research Administration as a Profession worldwide project's definition. The same definition was shared during the kick off meeting of the WG, along with the link to the LinkedIn group of the Sub-Working Group (**Annex II** – Questionnaire implemented via Google form).

The questionnaire was proposed to Italian RMAs through a formal channel, i.e. the CODAU Research mailing list, and through more informal channels, such as colleagues and professional acquaintances of the WG members. Out of 259 responses received, 139 were from universities in the North of Italy, 85 from universities in the Center, 11 from universities in the South and Islands³ and 24 records did not contain an indication of their pertaining university.

From an initial analysis of responses to the questionnaire (**WP3**), it emerged that the RMA profession is relatively new in the Italian context: more than 90% of the sample claim to have between 0 and 15 years of work experience in the sector and is equally divided between Managers and Administrators (about 40%), while only 15% claim to be Leader. Some interesting facts appear in relation to the activities carried out by each of the 3 levels: it occurs, in fact, that Managers and Administrators often carry out the same type of activity, and Leaders in some cases dedicate themselves to rather operational tasks. The answers provided could be influenced by a different interpretation of the definition of professional levels, not necessarily coinciding with the ones provided within the Italian national contractual conditions of professionals working at Universities (*CCNL – Contratto Collettivo Nazionale dei Lavoratori*: e.g. EP, D and C professional and salary categories) or to the lack of a shared definition among RMAs about the activities and the skills associated to each professional level.

An element that unites all professional levels is the need to receive continuous training (**WP5**). However, more than 90% of the sample stated to have received only certificate of attendance to training activities, with no formal recognition/accreditation of any professional title by Italian authorities (e.g. MUR – Ministry of Higher Education, Ministry of Labor, University, etc.), which may be used for career advancement purposes.

A report with a deeper level of analysis and a graphical representation of the results has been drafted and used for developing a professional reference framework proposal for Italian RMAs (Annex III).

The questionnaire results have been used for the creation of the **professional reference framework for Italian RMA (WP4)**, whose starting point is an initial, synthetic definition of the three professional levels of RMAs in Italy, as shared within the Working Group:

- *Leader* – Responsible for the strategic functions of the Institution
- *Manager* – Directly reporting to Leader and Responsible for a Team or for specific missions (regardless of formal appointment)
- *Administrator* – Responsible for specific and operational tasks.

The analysis of the questionnaire performed in WP3 revealed some critical issues and needs for further study in relation to the "self-placement" of respondents in one of the three categories, not only with reference to the activities carried out, but also in relation to the declared training needs.

The professional framework, therefore, offers both an inductive and deductive analysis, i.e. using the evaluation of the questionnaire administered to the Italian RMA community, as well as the knowledge of the national and international professional framework of RMAs. The latter is also confirmed by the benchmark

³ NUTS-EU classification.

activities carried out in WP1. Last but not least, the output of the CODAU sub-working group "Services to support participation in funding programs", coordinated by La Sapienza University, proved useful - with specific reference to the activities carried out by the RMAs. The final report of this sub-group is, in fact, a "Catalog of charts - good practices - and scalable initiative models" of the services offered by the "Research Offices", of the RMAs, in support of participation in funding programs, in particular European funding programs for R&I. The comparative analysis of the services provided and the direct comparison with a representation of researchers highlighted *"how the Research Offices actually represent atypical administrative offices, as they are considered owners of specialized skills on continuously evolving topics. The Research Offices are therefore considered as important points of connection between the Research area and the Administration of Universities"*.

Therefore, the following macro-areas of activities characterizing the scope of action of RMAs were first identified:

1. ORGANIZATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING OF THE RESEARCH MANAGEMENT SERVICE
2. PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH STRATEGIES AND POLICIES
3. PRE-AWARD PHASE: PARTNERSHIP, COLLABORATIONS, FUND RAISING, RESEARCH PLANNING
4. POST-AWARD PHASE: MANAGEMENT OF FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS
5. ETHICS, OPEN AND CITIZENS SCIENCE
6. EVALUATION OF RESEARCH

Each macro area was subsequently divided into specific tasks and activities related to the 3 professional levels. At the same time, both the knowledge and the soft skills that each RMA should have were attributed to every level (Annex IV).

The specific WP about dissemination (WP6) has three interrelated objectives: **raising awareness on the professional profile of RMAs at the Italian level**, both (i) among professionals working in field of research support and research management and (ii) in the framework of the Italian university system, where no accreditations nor certifications are yet adopted for the qualification/recognition/career development of RMAs, as well as (iii) establishing a connection with the international community of RMAs.

For these purposes, different actions have been undertaken:

- launch of a LinkedIn group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12369361/>) featuring almost 100 RMAs from both the academic and non-academic sector;
- consolidating connections with EARMA, the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators, and in particular with the Professional Development and Recognition Committee, which has been duly and timely informed about the activities of the WG;
- presentation of the WG activities at the EARMA2021 conference;
- drafting an article on the WG activities, which has been published on the APRE⁴ MAGAZINE in June 2020;
- linking with the European project foRMAtion (<https://www.formation-rma.eu/>) of which APRE is a partner.

Associations analysed in WP1 have been assessed as to identify relevant best practices on how they use their social profiles and accounts to generate awareness and to promote their initiatives and goals. All members of the WG have also been advised to inform the governance at their Universities on the WG progress and outcomes. Considering that the role of the Research Manager has been mentioned in the 2021 Italian

⁴ APRE (Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea) is the Italian executive Agency for the promotion of research on European funding. APRE acts as National Contact Point for a wide variety of European Funding Programmes supporting research.

National Plan for Research (PNR), contacts have been initiated with the Italian Ministry of Higher Education (MUR). The writing of an article to be submitted to an international journal is also underway (Annex III).

Relations were strengthened with the European association EARMA (European Association of Research Managers and Administrators) and in particular with the Professional Development and Recognition Committee, to which information on the activities of the WG - with particular reference to WP1 - was sent.

The activities of the subgroup were presented on April 15th 2021 at the EARMA2021 plenary conference and during one of EARMA's digital meetings on "The future RMA profession" (March 4th, 2021).

Also considering the inclusion of the role of the Research Manager in the PNR 2021 and within the new European Research Area, contacts have been initiated with the MUR and Bruxelles, along with expanded international contacts through the European Alliances of which some members of the subgroup are part. In particular, a presentation of the subgroup's activity to the European Alliance ARQUS is expected on May 4th 2021 (<https://www.arqus-alliance.eu/>). The activities of the subgroup will also be disseminated within the European Alliance UNITE! (<https://www.unite-university.eu/>), in which the creation of a network of research support personnel is planned.

WHAT NEXT?

The WG has decided to establish a permanent group in order to continue to enhance the professional role of the RMA within the Italian community, to strengthen collaboration at European and international level and to carry out activities related to future professional recognition, such as development of an ad hoc training and professionalization courses.

The **WP7** Management SubGroup Coordinators are the Politecnico di Torino and the University of Camerino.

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Annex I – Work Package 1

Benchmarking of data collected from RMA Associations worldwide and BESTPRAC COST Project

The collection of data was carried out by a *working group* of 12 Italian universities—set up within the Association of General Directors of Italian Universities (CoDAU)- aimed at creating a professional development framework for RMAs in Italy

NAME and COUNTRY	SCOPE	PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK	PROFESSIONAL LEVEL(S)	TRAINING and ACCREDITATION/ RECOGNITION	WEBSITE
ARMA (UK)	Founded in 1991, has over 3,000 individual members from around 250 organizations, ranging from Universities and Funding Bodies to the National Health Service and independent Research Institutions.	Yes, available on the website https://arma.ac.uk/professional-development/	Three professional levels.	Two certificates (Foundation and Advanced) accredited by Awards for Training and Higher Education (ATHE) https://arma.ac.uk/qualifications/ other than training events https://arma.ac.uk/events/	www.arma.ac.uk
ARMA-NL (the Netherlands)	Founded in 2018, following 10 years' activity as an information network. It includes professionals active in advice, management and administration of international as well as national financed research, innovation and education projects.	Under development.	Not yet available.	ARMA-NL is developing a program of certified training courses and workshops.	www.armanl.nl/web
ARMS (Australia, New Zealand and Singapore)	Founded in 1999, involves more than 3,000 members from universities, independent research institutions, government and health and research institutions.	Yes, available on the website https://www.researchmanagement.org.au/professional-development	Three levels for knowledge enhancement.	Two accreditation programs (Foundation and Advanced) https://www.researchmanagement.org.au/advanced-level-accreditation-program-opportunities-still-available-join-2020-cohort	www.researchmanagement.org.au
CARA-ACAAR (Canada)	Provides a critical interface between all stakeholders in the management of the research enterprise. Has more than 1,000 members.	Not Formally defined.	Not Formally defined.	Two programmes (fellowship and mentorship) and one certificate in Research Administration in partnership with Mohawk College. Another certificate in progress https://cara-acaar.ca/Programs/ProfessionalCertification	www.cara-acaar.ca
DARMA (Denmark)	Open to individuals working as research and development (R&D) managers or administrators, from all kinds of employers—universities, colleges, research institutes, hospitals, museums, companies, funders, agencies or any organisation engaged in scientific research.	Not formally defined.	Not formally defined.	DARMA organizes workshops, webinars, and courses.	www.darma.dk

NAME and COUNTRY	SCOPE	PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK	PROFESSIONAL LEVEL(S)	TRAINING and ACCREDITATION/ RECOGNITION	WEBSITE
EARMA (Europe)	Founded in 1995, EARMA represents the community of Research Managers and Administrators within Europe.	EARMA has not developed a framework but builds on the ARMA one.	Three professional levels.	One formally recognized certificate. One workshop for early stage RMA and a leadership programme https://www.earma.org/earma-academy/certificate-in-research-management/	www.earma.org
Finn-ARMA (Finland)	Founded in 2012 as a network of Finnish universities' research services, that support universities' research activities, including services e.g. in research funding, legal and contractual matters, innovation and entrepreneurship and research administration. It has 500 members.	Not formally defined.	Three professional levels.	Organizes professional training for its members.	www.finn-arma.fi
FORTRAMA (Germany)	The network FORTRAMA is an affiliation of professionals working in the fields of Research & Innovation management at German universities and other German research institutions. Founded in 2003, turned into an association in 2018.	Not formally defined but identified as a key task in FORTRAMA's statutes.	Not yet formally defined.	One professional development program, workshops (jointly offered with the Centre for Science and Research Management in Speyer https://www.zwm-speyer.de/) for research managers and other training activities.	www.fortrama.net
NARMA (Norway)	Norwegian Network for Administration and Research Management was established in 2013 by Universities Norway (UHR) has around 700 members.	Yes, info available on the website https://narma.no/professional-development-program/	Three professional levels.	One competence development program (info on the main page of the website, link in the next column).	www.narma.no/om-https://narma.no/om-narma/english-about-narma-and-contact/
NCURA (USA)	The National Council of University Research Administrators (NCURA), founded in 1959, is an organization of individuals with professional interests in the administration of sponsored programs (research, education and training), primarily at colleges and universities.	Not formally defined.	Not formally defined.	Organizes workshops, webinars, fellowship programs https://www.ncura.edu/Education.aspx	www.ncura.edu
Plataforma de Interface à Ciência (Portugal)	Informal network of science interface professionals, created in 2016.	Not formally defined.	Not formally defined.	Provides a short training session during its annual meeting	https://sites.google.com/view/pic-pt/home?authuser=0
RMAN -J (Japan)	Professional association for those engaged in research management and administration. It aims to promote science, technology, and future innovation from Japan through the enhancement of research capabilities of Japanese universities and research institutes. Founded in 2015.	Under development.	Three professional Levels.	Provides training opportunities for research managers and administrators in Japan.	http://www.rman.jp/
SARIMA (Southern Africa)	SARIMA is an organization that brings together Research & Innovation Management practitioners.	Yes, available in the website (developed in 2015-17) https://www.sarima.co.z	Three professional Levels.	Two Certificates, accredited by the International Professional Recognition Council (IPRC)	www.sarima.co.za/about

NAME and COUNTRY	SCOPE	PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK	PROFESSIONAL LEVEL(S)	TRAINING and ACCREDITATION/ RECOGNITION	WEBSITE
		a/resources/research-management/#01		https://www.sarima.co.za/professionalisation/	
Society of Research Administrators International (SRAI) (USA)	Founded in 1967 in US it evolved in 1998 when the word "International" was added to the Society's name. It's the premier global research management society providing education, professional development and the latest comprehensive information about research management to professionals from over 40 countries. It has 5,600 members from colleges and universities, research hospitals and institutes, government agencies, non-profit funders of research and industry.	Not formally defined.	Not formally defined.	Ten certificate programmes (https://www.srainternational.org/meetings/certificate-programs) LevelUP (https://www.srainternational.org/online-learning/levelup-main) Trainings and Conferences, Webinars, True-fit Training, Coffee Talks, Continuing Education Credit.	www.srainternational.org/home
BESTPRAC (COST Project)	COST Targeted Network (2014-19) that gathers administrative, financial and legal staff at universities and research-driven institutions who are carrying out different tasks to support transnational external competition based (in particular EU funded) research projects.	Yes, available on the website and wiki page. Activities defined according to the Project Cycle Management Phases http://www.bestprac-wiki.eu/Main_Page	Three types of research support staff.	During the project lifetime some training courses for RMA were provided by partner's institutions. https://bestprac.eu/training/general-information/	www.bestprac.eu/home

Source: Authors' analysis of associations' websites and interviews (June 2020). Authors: Valentina Romano (Politecnico di Torino, Italy), Adele Del Bello (University of Ferrara, Italy), Annalisa Albanesi (University of Camerino, Italy)

Annex II – Work Package 2

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was prepared with the purpose of working on the creation of a standard professional framework of the Research Manager and Administrator in Italian Universities, in order to raise awareness of the RMAs role and promote the potential of this profession within the RMA community in Italy.

The objective of the questionnaire has been the analysis of Italian RMAs' core activities and training needs.

The questionnaire results have provided useful data and insights on the Italian RMA professional profile, and have proved useful in developing a reference professional framework proposal. (1)

All responses were collected for scientific purposes only and within the scope of the present project. Personal data will be processed and managed in accordance to European legislation including the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679).

The questionnaire was elaborated via Google Forms⁵ and first launched on July 30th 2020. Deadline for submission was set on September 15th 2020.

The survey has been structured in three parts:

- part A - description of one's own experience as RMA
- part B - identification of training experiences
- part C - identification of training needs.

The RAAAP (Research Administration as a Profession worldwide project) definition of Research Manager and Administrator (RMA) was included. Link to the LinkedIn Group was also included.

PART A – EXPERIENCE AS RMA

1. What is the name of the institution you are working for?

2. How long have you been working in the field of Research Management & Administration (approx. no. years)?

3. With which professional level do you identify yourself? (as per the RAAAP Worldwide definition⁶ – Research Administration as a Profession Worldwide: <https://raapworldwide.wordpress.com/project>) – Choose only one option.

⁵ <https://forms.gle/G2sxme3smQMEQuoC9>

⁶ *The Research Manager Administrator is a person working to support the research lifecycle process. This includes (but is not limited to) the following tasks: strategic planning of research activities, organisation of services supporting researchers, lobbying, networking, promotion of research, pre-award and post-award project support (i.e. scouting of funding opportunities, support to project management - from drafting to submission – and to budgeting and cost planning, handling of internal institutional relations, negotiations with funders, partnership management, supervision of financial report towards funders). Support and advisor on research impacts, innovation and promotion, on training matters, on research policy, strategy and assessment and a number of topics such as data processing, research integrity, communication, ethics, governance, IT, audits, statutory returns, and career development of researchers.*

- *Leader* – Responsible for the strategic functions of the Institution
- *Manager* – Directly reporting to Leader and Responsible for a Team or for specific missions (regardless of formal appointment)
- *Administrator* – Responsible for specific and operational tasks

4. What is your current activity within your Institution? Choose one or more options.

- I am in charge of one or more specific activities
- I supervise a Team
- I manage a complex structure

5. What are the tasks connected to your job? Choose all applicable options.

- Support to governance in the strategic planning of research activities
- Planning of services to support research
- Lobbying activities; networking activities; promotion of research
- Pre award support (e.g. identification of funding opportunities, support for the preparation of project proposals, budget and cost plan elaboration, project submission)
- Post award support / project management (e.g. support for administrative and financial reporting, relations with the funders, audit support)
- Drafting and negotiation of contracts with funding bodies
- Support in maintaining relations with the partners and with internal institutional stakeholders
- Support and advice on the impact of research, enhancement of research (Technology Transfer)
- Planning and delivery of training courses for RMAs and researchers, support for the career development of researchers
- Support to research policies and strategies.
- Data processing, internal and external information systems
- Research integrity, research communication, ethics and RRI
- Other – please specify _____

PART B – TRAINING EXPERIENCES

6. Did you take part to training classes in the past 5 years, as a trainer/teacher? Choose only one option.

- Yes
- No

7. If you answered “Yes” to question 6, what is the name of the course and what institution organized it?

8. Did you take part to training classes in the past 5 years, as a student /trainer? Choose only one option.

- Yes
- No

Most RMAs work in universities or research institutes, but many researchers work in hospitals, institutions, charities, government bodies, corporations or other related organisations. The above definition is to be intended as general and does not relate to any specific individual institution.

9. If you answered “Yes” to question 8, what is the name of the course and what institution organized it?

10. If you answered “Yes” to question 8, what type of accreditation did you receive for attending the course?

11. Was the course useful/applicable to your daily job? Choose only one option.

- Yes
- No
- Partially

PART C – TRAINING NEEDS

12. How much importance do soft skills/cross functional skills have in your daily job? Choose only one option.

- Extremely important
- Relatively important
- Not important at all

13. Choose the level of importance of the following soft skills in your daily job. Ranking goes from 1 (not important at all) to 5 (extremely important). Choose only one option per skill.

• Communication skills	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Ability to motivate others	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Decision-making and Problem Solving	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Ability to innovate	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Ability to build Working Groups	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Leadership	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Conflict management	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Analytical attitude	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Communication skills	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• Mentoring and Coaching	<input type="checkbox"/>				

14. Choose the level of importance of the following technical skills in your daily job. Ranking goes from 1 (not important at all) to 5 (extremely important). Choose only one option per skill.

• Knowledge of European/National research strategies	<input type="checkbox"/>					
• Scientific/technical background	<input type="checkbox"/>					
• Project Management	<input type="checkbox"/>					

15. Complete the following sentence: “In terms of training needs, I would need.....” Choose all applicable options.

- Communication skills
- Ability to motivate others
- Decision-making and Problem Solving
- Ability to innovate
- Ability to build Working Groups
- Leadership
- Knowledge of European/National research strategies
- Project Management
- Other – please specify _____

16. Any additional suggestion/information you may want to share.

For more updates about the work group's activities, follow us on the dedicated WG LinkedIn group:

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12369361/>

Annex III - WP3 Questionnaire analysis Characteristics and training needs of the Italian RMAs

The starting point for a conceptual and operational definition of the Italian RMA has been the analysis of the activities, skills and knowledge identified within the professional frameworks of the international RMA associations analysed within Work Package 1 (WP1). The aim has been to classify professional levels and to establish a professional framework for the Italian RMA landscape.

A questionnaire was then designed in order to identify the characteristics and training needs of RMAs in Italy (WP2). Intentionally anonymous and easy-to-fill-out, the questionnaire investigated who the Italian RMAs are in terms of experiences, professional levels, work activities, training paths, hard and soft skills, and training needs.

The questionnaire, elaborated via Google Forms⁷, was structured in three parts:

- part A - description of one's own experience as RMA
- part B - identification of training experiences
- part C - identification of training needs.

The RAAAP (Research Administration as a Profession worldwide project) definition of Research Manager and Administrator (RMA) was included in the questionnaire. The RMA definition by RAAAP was also shared during the kick off meeting of the WG. The Questionnaire featured the link to the Sub-Group LinkedIn Group.

The questionnaire was shared with Italian RMAs through a formal channel, i.e. the CODAU Research mailing list⁸, and through the usual institutional communication channels (i.e. mailing lists) adopted by the Universities of the WG members.

The distribution of the answers highlights a greater awareness of and attention to the RMA topics in the universities of the North and Center of Italy and a greater understanding of the international context in which the RMA operates. In fact, out of 259 responses received, 139 were from universities in the North, 85 from universities in the Center, 11 from universities in the South and Islands (NUTS-EU classification³⁹), while 24 records did not contain an indication of the pertaining university.

PART A - THE ITALIAN RMA: DEFINING THE ROLE

The RMA profession is quite new in the Italian context: more than 90% of the sample tested claims to have between 0 and 15 years of work experience in the sector. Besides, the “self-assessment” responses with regards to the professional role level, are equally divided between Managers and Administrators (about 40%), whereas 15% self-declare as Leaders. The distribution is represented in

Chart 1: Sample distribution by professional role level

⁷ <https://forms.gle/G2sxme3smQMEQuoC9>

⁸ The CODAU Research Working Group has created a mailing list for the exchange of information between Italian RMAs. There are about 400 registered users.

⁹ NUTS-UE Classification (<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/it/sheet/99/nomenclatura-comune-delle-unita-territoriali-statistiche-nuts>)

Chart 1¹⁰: of the entire sample, Managers and Administrators (71%) represent the largest part, and in particular those who perform one or more specific activities. While the Managers manage small structures, Leaders manage complex organizational units.

Charts 2-4 show in detail such distribution.

Activities carried out by the Italian RMA almost entirely focus on the technical assistance embracing the whole PCM - Project Cycle Management of research projects carried out through International (or external) funding, that are typical of Grant Offices.

Chart 2: identification of Leader's role

From the pre-award to the post award phase, the Italian RMA guides and supports the researcher from the project idea to the very last report to the funding body. Substantially, the largest workload resides in the pre-award and post-award phases.

The collateral activities of networking, lobbying, general support, negotiation, training, policy implementation, IT, RRI are not evenly distributed, and are relevant to a varying 15% to 50% of the sample examined.

PART B - EXISTING TRAINING COURSES FOR THE RMAs IN ITALY

The Italian RMA does not seem to be particularly involved in training activities as a trainer (only 30%) whereas its expertise may be particularly useful to colleagues and researchers managing international project activities. In fact, the *design, management and financial reporting of projects financed through European funds* is a recurrent topic in courses in which RMAs act as trainers.

The RMA proves to be very up-to-date and focused on the continuous procedural changes and evolutions of European and national legislations.

In fact, RMAs are regularly accessing training opportunities: 85% of the survey sample declares to have attended PCM training courses in the last 5 years, provided by accredited Italian and European trainers

Chart 3: Identification of Manager's role

Chart 4: Identification of Administrator's role

⁴ [ed.] Answers, which were different from the given questionnaire's selections, have been incorporated - whenever possible - within the identified categories (e.g. "I manage the Research Office" and "Secretariat Manager" blend in the "I manage a complex structure" category). If the merging was not possible, the answers were omitted, for the sole purpose of computation.

belonging to the international research system. Participants considered these courses useful for the execution of their daily tasks, in 74% of cases.

On the other hand, data regarding the formal certification of such trainings seems unsatisfactory: over 90% of the sample did receive a declaration of attendance, yet no formal recognition is provided by Italian authorities (e.g. MIUR – Ministry of Education and Higher Education, Ministry of Labour, own University etc.) and no professional accreditation is certified. A formal recognition of acquired competences and experience could prove useful when competing in public calls and could facilitate career development of RMAs, both within and outside their employer. Overall, the profession of Italian RMAs seems valuable, yet still “unqualified” and therefore “invisible” in the Italian job market.

It is noticeable that training providers are mostly Universities, including Higher Education Institutions in which RMAs work. Trainers themselves are often RMAs.

TRAINING NEEDS FOR THE RMAs IN ITALY (PART C)

It is impressive how data on the training needs identified by the Italian RMAs prove a substantial demand for further training on project management, design, innovation and communication. Data also show that RMAs pay particular attention on being up-to-date, especially about the European and international regulations and procedures, whose knowledge and good command is essential to effectively reconcile such regulations and procedures with the ones at the national and regional level.

Among those who declared having held trainings as teachers (74 cases out of 259), the category of Managers (32 cases) emerges, as compared to that of Leaders (17) and that of Administrators (25).

The category that has been more extensively involved in the attendance of training courses (out of 251 cases) is that of Administrators (94), as compared to Managers (85) and Leaders (33). Three (3) respondents did not comment on the subject.

Chart 5: The importance of Cross-Functional Skills

The Italian RMA must also feature effective cross-functional and soft skills, in particular in the area of decision-making and complex problem solving, along with the ability to cope with information management and with multifaceted situations, while keeping in mind the European legislation and procedures, the international, national and internal administrative and management regulations. Chart 5 shows the level of importance attributed to each cross-functional competence identified in the questionnaire.

Flexibility and resilience appear as the main characteristics of the RMA at all three levels of Leader, Manager and Administrator, combined with a good amount of creativity, communication and motivational skills. Chart 6 illustrates the average importance recognized to each soft skill.

Chart 6: The importance of soft skills

Chart 7 shows in detail the soft skills that are perceived as most relevant to each RMA level.

Chart 7: The most relevant soft skills

The RMA attaches great importance to the command of technical skills on project management as well as knowledge on the European and national strategic contexts, on social and economic policies. Scientific expertise appears to be less important, as the RMA provides its advice on PCM to the entire class of researchers, regardless of the research area.

CRITICAL ISSUES AND TAKE HOME MESSAGE

The objective of the WG is to identify and describe the professional profile of the Research Manager, and to define in detail the different skills featuring this professional appointment; to this purpose, the analysis of the questionnaire has been preparatory to the definition of a professional framework proposal for Italian RMAs. The RMA appears as a definitely multifaceted role, characterized by a distinctive mixture of hard and soft skills.

On one hand, the survey provided an extensive list of soft skills options, including the ability of managing the project life cycle, the ability to coordinate working groups, the ability to manage conflict and to problem solving, the ability to motivate people and to master an innovation driven attitude. On the other, when collecting information and ideas on the level of background knowledge and hard skills associated to the RMA profile, only three options were available. The fact that the questionnaire gives much importance to appraising cross-functional skills could be corrected in a future survey. A better understanding of basic and advanced competences specific to research support services could actually prove very useful when designing any dedicated training. The overall results suggest that it may be relevant to develop and experiment a system of formally accredited qualifications, overcoming the current main reliance on simple certificates of attendance to trainings, where no specific recognition of RMA teaching is in fact allowed. It could be interesting in the near future to verify if and how such “attended” trainings, which lack a formal institutional accreditation, actually have some influence when it comes to career development (and economic progression) of RMAs.

Annex IV – WP 4 A professional framework for the Research Manager & Administrator (RMA) role in Italy

For the purpose of creating a national professional framework for the Research Manager and Administrator role, the WG agreed to use the RMA definition developed by the RAAAP - Research Administration as a Profession worldwide (<https://inorms.net/activities/raaap-taskforce/>) as a reference and starting point. Such definition matches more closely the Italian RMA core activities and adapts fairly well to the Italian context.

The Research Manager Administrator according to RAAAP - The Research Manager Administrator is a person working to support the research lifecycle process. This includes (but is not limited to) the following tasks: strategic planning of research activities, organisation of services supporting researchers, lobbying, networking, promotion of research, pre-award and post-award project support (i.e. scouting of funding opportunities, support to project management - from drafting to submission – and to budgeting and cost planning, handling of internal institutional relations, negotiations with funders, partnership management, supervision of financial report towards funders). Support and advisor on research impacts, innovation and promotion, on training matters, on research policy, strategy and assessment and a number of topics such as data processing, research integrity, communication, ethics, governance, IT, audits, statutory returns, and career development of researchers.

The development of a professional framework proposal for Italian RMAs was based on) a deductive and inductive assessment of WP1 and WP2 outcomes. The WG formulated a template based on the RMA questionnaire analysis, which was carried out in WP2, and on the consideration of international professional frameworks of RMAs collected within the benchmarking activity performed in WP1.

First, the macro-areas of activities characterizing the scope of action of RMAs were identified. Each macro area was subsequently divided into tasks/activities, and assigned to three different levels as assessed in the existing international RMAs frameworks, and adjusted to the Italian context:

RMA LEVELS

1. *Leader* – Responsible for the strategic functions of the Institution
2. *Manager* – Directly reporting to Leader and Responsible for a Team or for specific missions (regardless of formal appointment)
3. *Administrator* – Responsible for specific and operational tasks

MACRO AREAS OF ACTIVITY

1. ORGANIZATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING OF THE RESEARCH MANAGEMENT SERVICE
2. PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH STRATEGIES AND POLICIES
3. PRE-AWARD PHASE: PARTNERSHIP, COLLABORATIONS, FUND RAISING, RESEARCH PLANNING
4. POST-AWARD PHASE: MANAGEMENT OF FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS
5. OPEN AND CITIZENS SCIENCE
6. EVALUATION OF RESEARCH

LIST OF TASKS FOR EACH MACRO AREA OF ACTIVITY

1. ORGANIZATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING OF THE RESEARCH MANAGEMENT SERVICE

1.1. **An outcome-oriented organizational environment.** Creating an organizational culture which recognizes and values research management, while supporting human resources development at all levels, in order to increase awareness and confidence and thus improving performance and productivity

1.2. **Team Management.** Understanding the requirements and needs of research support, proposing innovative strategies for the development and growth of the research management service

1.3. **Team Work.** Working together and staying open to comparison and debate also within the same organization, with the awareness of research processes

2. PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH STRATEGIES AND POLICIES

2.1. **Support and monitor the implementation of research strategies and policies,** suggesting strategic paths and perspectives to increase the organization's research portfolio, also by promoting a public, national and international profile of its research organization system

2.2. **Promote lobbying actions** at the main funding bodies, associations and interest groups with reference to research funding strategies and practices

2.3. **Apply and monitor research policy and regulatory best practices,** including through benchmarking activities

3. PRE-AWARD PHASE: PARTNERSHIP, COLLABORATIONS, FUND RAISING, RESEARCH PLANNING

3.1. **Create opportunities to promote partnerships and collaborations** with public and private institutions, stakeholders and funders, **identify actions to support the career and professional development** of researchers, in line with the strategic objectives defined by the governance, and ensure the diversification of the funding portfolio

3.2. **Manage and promote the partnerships and collaborations activated, also identifying the main sources of funding for research,** guaranteeing their visibility with internal stakeholders, **promoting actions to support the career and professional development of researchers** and **monitoring the presentation of research project proposals**

3.3. **Implement research project management,** supporting internal communication of funding opportunities and drafting project proposals for research funding

4. POST-AWARD PHASE: MANAGEMENT OF FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS

4.1. **Supervise the general framework of project management and guide organizational policies** for the best possible management of funded projects, also in terms of allocation of dedicated human resources and / or of access to facilities for carrying out research activities

4.2. **Develop best practices in the management of funded projects,** promote internal and external benchmarks and encourage constant contact with funding bodies and relevant stakeholders

4.3. **Manage the funded project**, from the negotiation phase to the review phase in accordance with the specific provisions of the funding body and the rules and best practices defined in the organization

5. OPEN AND CITIZEN SCIENCE

5.1. **Promote and disseminate** the principles of open and citizens' science within the organization, also by encouraging the implementation of regulations, codes and practices, participation in national and international networks on the subject and working to achieve the related third-mission objectives

5.2. **Ensure constant updates on the issues of open and citizens' science**, also by promoting internal information / training moments, and planning activities for the dissemination and communication of research and its results

5.3. **Become acquainted with the principles of open and citizens' science**, and convey them through project proposals, *ad hoc* information / training modules, dissemination and communication activities about research and its results

6. EVALUATION OF RESEARCH

6.1. **Support governance** in the implementation of national and internal policies for the evaluation of research and researchers, in the monitoring and reporting of data and research activities

6.2. **Coordinate the specific national and / or internal evaluation campaigns** of research and researchers, supervising the collection of the necessary information, also according to the monitoring and reporting activities of the research

6.3. **Manage and support the collection of data** in relation to the research evaluation partners and researchers and for the purposes of monitoring and reporting on research

The specific tasks (activities) within the macro-activities, the expertise (hard skills), the competencies (soft skills) and the training needs, were subsequently associated with each of the three RMA levels initially identified.

This association is not necessarily rigid, i.e. it does not imply that a task shall be associated with only one RMA level. In fact, even from the questionnaire's answers, it appears that the same activity can often be carried out by professionals at different levels, considering the operational context of reference. What changes between the different professional levels is therefore not only the type of activity, but sometimes also (or maybe only) the way in which the activity is executed, in terms of requested knowledge and skills.

Last but not least, it should be emphasized that some of the activities described above are carried out in collaboration with other professional profiles, not necessarily belonging to the RMA category, such as, for example, the professionals dedicated to bibliographic support (e.g. open science → open access & research repositories) or to the support of some specific activities of third-mission and communication.

1. LEADER

A. ACTIVITIES

1.1 - **An outcome-oriented organizational environment**: creating an organizational culture which recognizes and values research management, while supporting human resources

development at all levels, in order to increase awareness and confidence and thus improving performance and productivity;

2.1. **Support and monitor the implementation of research strategies and policies**, suggesting strategic paths and perspectives to increase the organization's research portfolio, also by promoting a public, national and international profile of its research organization system

3.1. **Create opportunities to promote partnerships and collaborations** with public and private institutions, stakeholders including funders, **identify actions to support the career and professional development** of researchers, in line with the strategic objectives defined by the governance, and ensure the diversification of the funding portfolio

4.1. **Supervise the general framework of project management and guide organizational policies** for the best possible management of funded projects, also in terms of allocation of dedicated human resources and / or of access to facilities for carrying out research activities

5.1. **Promote and disseminate** the principles of open and citizens' science within the organization, also by encouraging the implementation of regulations, codes and practices, participation in national and international networks on the subject and working to achieve the related third-mission objectives

6.1. **Support governance** in the implementation of national and internal policies for the evaluation of research and researchers, in the monitoring and reporting of data and research activities

B. EXPERTISE (HARD SKILLS)

Knowledge must be functional to the effective performance of the activities listed above:

- Project Management, organization, development of human resources
- National, European and international research policies, with reference to research funding, evaluation, endorsement and communication
- English language

C. COMPETENCIES (SOFT SKILLS)

Set of skills necessary to carry out the activities described above:

- Leadership and motivational skills
- Results-driven
- Interpersonal and networking skills

2. MANAGER

A. ACTIVITIES

1.2. **Team Management**: understanding the requirements and needs of research support, proposing innovative strategies for the development and growth of the research management service

2.2. **Promote lobbying actions** at the main funding bodies, associations and interest groups with reference to research funding strategies and practices

3.2. **Manage and promote the partnerships and collaborations activated, also identifying the main sources of funding for research**, guaranteeing their visibility with internal stakeholders, **promoting actions to support the career and professional development of researchers** and **monitoring the presentation of proposals for research project**

4.2. **Develop best practices in the management of funded projects**, promote internal and external benchmarks and encourage constant contact with funding bodies and relevant stakeholders

5.2. **Ensure constant updates on the issues of open and citizens' science**, also by promoting internal information / training moments, and planning activities for the dissemination and communication of the research and its results

6.2. **Coordinate the specific national and / or internal evaluation campaigns** of research and researchers, supervising the collection of the necessary information, also according to the monitoring and reporting activities of the research

B. EXPERTISE (HARD SKILLS)

Knowledge must be functional to the effective performance of the activities listed above:

- National and European research policies, Italian and European research “eco-system”, with reference to research funding, evaluation and communication;
- main national, European and international research funding programs;
- tools and portals dedicated to project management and monitoring of data and products of research activities
- English language

C. COMPETENCIES (SOFT SKILLS)

Set of skills necessary to carry out the activities described above:

- Leadership and ability to coordinate a team
- Interpersonal and communication skills at different levels, with internal and external stakeholders
- Problem solving and results-driven

3. ADMINISTRATOR

A. ACTIVITIES

1.3. **Team Work:** working together and staying open to comparison and debate also within the same organization, with the awareness of research processes

2.3. **Apply and monitor research policy and regulatory best practices**, including through benchmarking activities

3.3. **Implement research project management**, supporting internal communication of funding opportunities and drafting project proposals for research funding

4.3. **Manage the funded project**, from the negotiation phase to the review phase in accordance with the specific provisions of the funding body and the rules and best practices defined in the organization

5.3. **Become acquainted with the principles of open and citizens' science**, and convey them through project proposals, *ad hoc* information / training modules, dissemination and communication activities about research and its results

6.3. **Manage and support the collection of data** in relation to the research evaluation partners and researchers and for the purposes of monitoring and reporting on research

B. EXPERTISE (HARD SKILLS)

Knowledge must be functional to the effective performance of the activities listed above:

- National and European research policies
- techniques for designing and drafting project proposals within the main research funding programs
- basic regulation knowledge of the main national, European and international research funding programs
- IT tools, software and platforms dedicated to project management and monitoring of data and products of research activities
- National legislation and internal regulation with reference to the activities carried out
- English language

B. COMPETENCIES (SOFT SKILLS)

Set of skills necessary to carry out the activities described above:

- Team Working
- Interpersonal Problem solving skills
- Communication skills
- Results-driven

RMA PROFESSIONAL FRAMEWORK - SUMMARY CHART

Leader

TECHNICAL SKILLS

Project management, organization, development of human resources

National, European and international research policies, with reference to research funding, evaluation, endorsement and communication

English language

SOFT SKILLS

Leadership and motivational skills
Results-driven
Interpersonal and networking skills

Manager

TECHNICAL SKILLS

National and European research policies, Italian and European research "eco-system", with reference to research funding, evaluation and communication

Main national, European and international research funding programs

Tools and portals dedicated to project management and monitoring of data and products of research activities

English language

SOFT SKILLS

Leadership and ability to coordinate a team
Interpersonal and communication skills at different levels, with internal and external stakeholders
Problem solving and results-driven

Administrator

TECHNICAL SKILLS

National and European research policies

Techniques for drafting project proposals within the main research funding programs

Basic regulation knowledge of European and international research funding programs

IT tools, software and portals dedicated to project management and monitoring of data and products of research activities

National legislation and internal regulation with reference to the activities carried out

English language

SOFT SKILLS

Team Working
Interpersonal Problem solving skills
Communication skills
Results-driven

RMA PROFESSIONAL FRAMEWORK PROPOSAL MATRIX

	ORGANIZATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING OF THE RESEARCH MANAGEMENT SERVICE	PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH STRATEGIES AND POLICIES	PRE-AWARD PHASE: PARTNERSHIP, COLLABORATIONS , FUND RAISING, RESEARCH PLANNING	POST-AWARD PHASE: MANAGEMENT OF FUNDED RESEARCH PROJECTS	ETHICS, OPEN AND CITIZENS SCIENCE	EVALUATION OF RESEARCH
Leader – Responsible for the strategic functions of the Institution	An outcome-oriented organizational environment	Support and monitor the implementation of research strategies and policies	Create opportunities to promote partnerships and collaborations	Supervise the general framework of project management and guide organizational policies	Promote and disseminate	Support governance in the implementation of national and internal policies
Manager – Directly reporting to Leader and Responsible for a Team or for specific missions (regardless of formal appointment)	Team Management	Promote lobbying actions	Manage and promote the partnerships and collaborations activated, also identifying the main sources of funding for research	Develop best practices in the management of funded projects	Ensure constant updates on the issues of open and citizens' science	Coordinate the specific national and / or internal evaluation campaigns of research and researchers
Administrator – Responsible for specific and operational tasks	Team Work	Apply and monitor research policy and regulatory best practices	Implement research project management	Manage the funded project	Become familiar with the principles of open and citizens' science and convey them through project proposals	Manage and support the collection of data in relation to the research partners evaluation